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Editor-in-Chief
Dr. Amit Jain

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Plea Bargaining Best Resource As An ADR Mechanism

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ABSTRACT

An agreement as a result of negotiation between the prosecution and defense at time, which settles a criminal case, usually in exchange for a more lenient punishment. Typically the defendant will plead guilty to a lesser crime or for a fewer charges than originally charged, in exchange for a more lenient punishment than the defendant would get if convicted at trial. It is seen as a win-win for all the parties as the prosecution has a certain conviction on the record, the defendant is provided a more lenient sentence than the risk of a higher one at trial and the judge is freed to move to other cases and dispute to resolve. Plea Bargaining can conclude a criminal case without a trial. When it is successful, Plea Bargaining results in a plea agreement between the prosecutor and defendant. In this agreement, the defendant agrees to plead guilty without a trial, and, in return the prosecutor agrees to dismiss certain charges or make favorable sentence recommendation to the court. Plea Bargaining can be described as a process whereby the accused may bargain with the prosecution for a lesser punishment. The litigant should be encouraged to avail the remedy of plea-bargaining to settle the pending cases. For the successful implementation of plea-bargaining, its application should be necessarily understandable. With the changing world scenario where all the countries are shifting to Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) mechanism from the traditional litigation process which is very lengthy and time consuming, the plea-bargaining may be one of the best recourse as an ADR mechanism to meet the challenges of disposal of pending cases.

A new chapter on Plea Bargaining has been introduced in the Criminal Procedure Code. It was introduced through the Criminal Law (Amendment) Act, 2005, which was passed by the Parliament in its winter session. It became effective from 5th July 2006. Originally Plea Bargaining is an American concept its origin can be traced back in America during the 19th Century. Over the years Plea bargaining has emerged as a prominent feature of the American Judicial System. In India Plea Bargaining has certainly changed the face of the Indian Criminal Justice System. Plea Bargaining is applicable in respect of those offences for which punishment is up to a period of 7 years. Moreover it does not apply to cases where the offence committed is a Socio-Economic offence or where the offence is committed against woman or a child below the age of 14 years. Also once the court passes an order in the case of Plea Bargaining no appeal shall lie to any court against that order.

As per Black Law Dictionary define, "Plea-bargaining is the process whereby the accused and the prosecutor in a criminal case work out a mutually satisfactory disposition of the case subject to the court approval. It usually involves the defendant's pleading guilty to lesser offence as to only one or some of the counts of a multi-count indictment in return for a lighter sentence than that possible for the graver charge". Therefore, it can be said that plea-bargaining refers to pre-trial negotiations between the defendant through his/her counsel and the prosecution during which the accused agrees to plead guilty in exchange for lesser

punishment.

It is applicable only in respect of those offences for which punishment of imprisonment is up to a period of 7 years.

It does not apply where such offence affects the socio-economic condition of the country or has been committed against a woman or a child below the age of 14 years. The application should be filed by the accused voluntarily. An accused must file an application for Plea-bargaining in the court in which such offence is pending for trial. The accused and prosecution both are given time to work out a mutually satisfactory disposition of the case, which may include giving compensation to the victim by the accused and other legal expenses incurred during pendency of the case. Where a satisfactory disposition of the case has been worked out, the Court shall dispose of the case by sentencing the accused to one-fourth of the punishment provided or extendable, as the case may be for such offence. The statement or facts stated by an accused in an application for plea-bargaining shall not be used for any other purpose other than for plea-bargaining. The judgment delivered by the Court in the case of plea-bargaining shall be final and no appeal shall lie in any court against such judgment. There are three essential conditions for the filing of an application of plea-bargaining: firstly, Accused voluntariness to plead guilty, secondly, The statements or facts stated by an accused in the application for plea-bargaining should not be used for any other purpose except plea-bargaining, and thirdly, It is a contractual agreement between the prosecution and the defendant regarding the disposition of criminal charge. However, it is not enforceable until a judge approves it. It generally occurs prior to the trial, but in some cases, it may occur anytime before a verdict is rendered or not. It is derogation from the concept that 'a judge can only decide a sentence after hearing in an open court'. Initially it was not recognized under Indian Law; therefore, not much importance was given to it as it was not in statutes. Reference may, however, be made to Section 206(1) and 206(3) of the Code of Criminal Procedure and Section 208(1) of the Motor Vehicles Act, 1988. These provisions enable the accused to plead guilty for petty offences or less grave offences and to pay small offences whereupon the case is closed. Later on, on the basis of US, our Law Commission recommended the application of plea-bargaining in India. They also justified the reasons for the same.

There are three types of Plea Bargain: namely Charge Bargain, Sentence Bargain and Fact Bargain. In Charge Bargaining, It is a bargain or promise between the prosecutor and defendant to deduct some of the charges brought against the defendant in exchange of guilty acceptance. When accused accepts for guilty that he has committed the wrong then with the approval of prosecution, there can be charge bargaining but it solely depends upon the will of prosecution. Prosecution may accept or neglect it. After charge bargaining the defendant will face specific charge. In Sentence Bargaining, it is a promise by the prosecutor, after acceptance of guilty; to recommend the court specific sentence or bargained sentence or it can be done directly with the trial judge. For this purpose, accused must be informed about the sentence likely to be imposed in case he does not accept his guilt but if he does so then prosecutor demands for lesser sentence or favorable sentence instead of what he was demanding earlier because of showing some sort of innocence regarding his guilt or for saving court's time.

This concept has not emerged recently but existed even in 19th century. In the United States, plea-bargaining is a significant part of the criminal justice system, majority of criminal cases are settled by plea-bargaining rather than by a trial by jury. But it is subject to the approval of the court. The rules pertaining to Plea-bargaining in all states of US are different. More than 90% of the cases are settled through Plea-bargaining in US. It has become a prominent

feature of American Judiciary that the disposing rate of cases is very rapid therefore, backlog is under control. Prosecutor initiates about the plea-bargaining proceedings. One of the main arguments advanced in the favour of plea-bargaining is that it helps in speedy disposal of accumulated cases and will expedite delivery of criminal justice. In India, position is very different from US. As it came in the amendment Act of 2005 in Code of Criminal Procedure, there are not much cases regarding it but even though, position under Indian Judiciary is very clear. There were huge debates on this point before it was inserted in the Cr.P.C. till 2005; it was not accepted by the Indian Judiciary. Every time it was opposed by court of law by saying that it is not recognized under Indian law and other reasons. The concept is not widely recognized and because there are cases, in which it was not applied properly. The initiation of plea-bargaining has to be by accused which is different from US Law. Our law provides for number of negotiations between the accused and the prosecutor or with the court itself which is a cardinal difference from US. Unlike in US, where plea-bargaining is for all sort of offences but in India, it is not for socio economic offences or the offences against women and children. Court has to take great care at the time of application of plea-bargaining. Speedy trial is the essence of criminal justice and there can be no doubt, if there is delay in trial by itself, constitutes denial of justice. Section 265-A to 265-L provides for the plea-bargaining under Code of Criminal Procedure. It is a devise which ensures that victims receive acceptable justice in reasonable time without risking the prospects of hostile witness, inordinate delay and non-affordable costs.

This principle is not applicable for hard crimes or serious crimes, therefore, Indian Law does not provides plea-bargaining for the offences in which (a) offence punishable with death or imprisonment for life; (b) punishable with imprisonment for a term exceeding 7 years; (c) committed against socio economic conditions of the country; (d) offence committed against women and children below the age of 14 years.

The judgment of plea-bargaining cases are final and no appeal lies on such judgment. However, a writ petition to the State High Court under Article 226 and 227 of the Constitution or a Special leave petition to the Supreme Court under Article 136 of the Constitution can be filed by the accused. This acts as a check on illegal and unethical Bargains. The provisions also authorize the court to give accused the benefit of Probation of Offenders Act where so ever it is possible. Section 12 of the Probation of Offenders Act, 1958 provides that a person found guilty of an offence and dealt with under section 3 or 4 of the said Act, shall not suffer any disqualification attached to the conviction. Thus, the Government employees who are released on probation under the Probation of offenders Act are saved from the disqualification, attached to this. The litigant should be encouraged to avail the remedy of plea-bargaining to settle the pending cases. For the successful implementation of plea-bargaining, its application should be necessarily understandable. With the changing world scenario where all the countries are shifting to ADR mechanism from the traditional litigation process which is very lengthy and time consuming, the plea-bargaining may be one of the best recourse as an ADR mechanism to meet the challenges of disposal of pending cases. There are other reasons also for backlog of cases. Even if everything is in order there are simply not enough mechanisms available to try a person. For example, in India, there are not enough courts to deal with the number of cases pending. There are also shortages of public prosecutors due to backlog in appointments.

Speedy trial is the essence of criminal justice and there is no doubt that delays in trial itself constitutes denial of justice. Initially, the concept of plea bargaining was criticized by a group of society including legal experts and intellectuals by stating that it will demoralize the

public confidence in criminal justice system and also lead to lesser penalties to rich class, conviction of innocent people and therefore, it has become disputed concept now. Today, plea bargain is used by all great countries like USA, Europe, Canada and some authorities stated that the prevalent conditions in India are very different from US, even then to meet out the huge backlog of cases in India and ultimately it will have to be done with the consent of both the parties i.e. accused and prosecution. Therefore, India cannot abstain itself for this law. This practice has been accepted by Indian Judiciary. It can reduce the heavy backlog of cases in Indian courts; as it requires today and we hope that overburdened criminal courts will soon get a relief with it and rate of disposing will become rapid. When the process is complete and the quantum of punishment and possibility of the probation is finished, we can say that the victims are not the forgotten actor rather they have become a key player in the criminal justice system. More than 3.5 crore cases are pending in Indian Courts. Plea-bargaining will solve cases involving petty offences and the courts will concentrate on more serious offences. Plea- bargaining will help in reducing backlog under Indian Judiciary and number of prisoners in jails also although the Constitutional obligation to provide speedy trial is also being fulfilled.

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